

Titrimetric Determination of Chloral Hydrate by Oxidation with Alkaline Potassium Permanganate

S. P. CHOUKSEY and R. M. VERMA*

Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, University of Jabalpur, Jabalpur (M.P.)

Manuscript received 7 May 1977, accepted 23 August 1977

A procedure is described for the volumetric determination of chloral hydrate based on its oxidation at ordinary temperature with alkaline permanganate in the presence of barium ions. Chloral hydrate (40-400 mg) can be determined by the proposed method with a precision of $\pm 0.8\%$ or better,

POTASSIUM dichromate¹, iodine^{2,3}, bromine⁴ and acidic potassium permanganate (in presence of sodium pyrophosphate)⁵ have been utilized for the quantitative oxidation of chloral hydrate. Stanciu and Stoicescu⁶ heated chloral hydrate with permanganate in presence of sodium carbonate and determined the unused oxidant iodometrically. This method cannot give accurate results because alkaline permanganate undergoes auto-decomposition on heating⁷.

In the present communication, alkaline permanganate has been used for the quantitative oxidation of chloral hydrate at room temperature. In strong alkaline solution the reduction of permanganate takes place in two steps. Manganate ion is formed in the first stage which gets further reduced to manganese dioxide in the second⁸. However, in presence of barium chloride, due to poor solubility of barium manganate, the manganate ion concentration is suppressed and hence the decomposition of manganate ion to manganese dioxide is prevented. This fact has been made use of in the proposed method for the determination of chloral hydrate.

Experimental

Sodium oxalate and potassium permanganate used were of A.R. quality. 0.1M solution of potassium permanganate was prepared⁹ and standardized against sodium oxalate solution¹⁰. Saturated solution of barium chloride and 10M sodium hydroxide solution were prepared from B.D.H. and E. Merck product respectively. Chloral hydrate solution of different concentrations were prepared by dissolving Carnegie Chemicals Limited product in distilled water and standardized with iodine solution.²

The oxidation of chloral hydrate with alkaline permanganate is rather slow. Hence, if alkaline permanganate solution is titrated rapidly with a solution of chloral hydrate, the reaction is incomplete and so more volume of chloral hydrate is required than calculated theoretically. On doing

the titration too slowly the auto-decomposition of permanganate occurs considerably and the titre value obtained is less than the stoichiometric value. This difficulty has been obviated in the following manner.

Procedure

25 ml of 0.1M potassium permanganate and 10 ml each of 10M sodium hydroxide and saturated barium chloride solutions are taken in an Erlenmeyer flask. The mixture is heated to about 80° and titrated (in 2-3 minutes) with the solution of chloral hydrate to be determined. The approximate titre so obtained is noted. The same reaction mixture is again taken, the volume of chloral hydrate corresponding to approximate titre is at once added and it is stirred for about 5 minutes. Chloral hydrate solution is very slowly added through a microburette with constant stirring till the pink colour disappears. The rate of addition of titre is so adjusted that about 15 minutes are required for the completion of titration.

1 ml of 0.1M potassium permanganate \equiv 8.271 mg of chloral hydrate.

The results for the evaluation of chloral hydrate solution of different concentrations have been recorded in Table-1.

Expt. No.	Chloral hydrate used for titration (M)	Amount of chloral hydrate on base of 2 electron change (mg)		Error
		Theoretical	Obtained	
1.	2.0000	418.550	410.241	-0.8
2.	0.2000	26.775	26.750	0.0
3.	0.0500	82.710	83.371	+0.8
4.	0.0125	41.355	41.670	+0.7

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the authors are due to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for the award of a fellowship to one of them (S.P.C.) and to Prof. G. S. Misra, Head of the Department of Chemistry, University of Jabalpur for providing necessary facilities for this work.

References

1. O.N. KARPOV, *Inst. Geokhim. i. Analit Khim*, 1963, **13**, 132.
2. I. M. KOLTHOFF, *Pharm. Weekblad*, 1923, **60**, 2.
3. In part Ph. D. Thesis of G. P., Soni, Jabalpur University, Jabalpur, 1971.
4. A. SCHWICKER, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1937, **110**, 161.
5. J. H. VAN DER MEULAN, *Chem. Weekblad*, 1949, **45**, 91.
6. N. STANCIU and V. STOICESCU, *Farmacia*, 1956, **4**, 313.
7. I.M. KOLTHOFF and R. BELCHOR, "Volumetric Analysis", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1957, Vol. III. p. 39.
8. J. HOLLUTTA, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1925, **115**, 137.
9. S. SHAPIRO and Ya GURVICH, "Analytical Chemistry", Mir Publishers, Moscow, 1972, p. 336-337.
10. R. M. FOWLER and H. A. BRIGHT, *J. Research Ntl. Bur. Standards*, 1935, **15**, 498.